

Review of Digital Platforms and Their Impact on Farmer-Centric and Transparent Practices

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Abstract:- This study explores the transformative impact of cutting-edge digital platforms on the dynamics of agricultural trade, emphasizing four key initiatives. The "Virtual Fruits Market" serves as a catalyst for direct farmer-consumer engagement, guaranteeing equitable pricing and establishing connections between farmers and industry specialists. In parallel, the online marketplace optimizes supply chains, empowering manufacturers to directly distribute agrochemicals. A farmer-centric mobile application facilitates direct produce sales, providing market insights in the farmers' native language. Another initiative introduces an online marketplace for direct transactions, ensuring fair pricing through quality evaluations by agriculture specialists. Lastly, an online auction system eliminates intermediaries, enabling consumers to competitively bid for farm produce. These endeavors collectively signify a paradigm shift toward transparent, farmer-centric, and digitally-driven advancements in the agricultural trade landscape.

Keywords:- Android Application; Seed Suggestion ;Activity Tracking; Connecting Farmer; Technical Guidance; Yield Analysis ; Soil Type ; Procedure Display ; Weather Condition.

I. INTRODUCTION

Farmers frequently face difficulties in the agricultural industry because of middlemen who interrupt the normal flow of the product supply chain. This exploitation is exacerbated by farmers' lack of access to critical information and assistance, their isolation from changes in other parts of the country, and a general lack of understanding of developing market technologies. Addressing these difficulties is critical for the agriculture sector's long-term growth. Among the numerous programs aimed to help farmers, our creative idea stands out. It aims to close gaps in the agricultural landscape by connecting farmers, providing access to low-cost agricultural inputs, showcasing successful procedures and actions taken by farmers to achieve the highest quality harvest, and providing comprehensive assistance throughout the farming process.

II. LITETURE REVIEW

The Virtual Fruits Market app enables Indian farmers to engage directly with end users while selling their fruit at a fair and consistent price. This ensures that farmers earn a bigger return on their products, while end customers benefit from cheaper pricing and higher-quality commodities from the farmers. Furthermore, the software links farmers with specialists who can give answers, helping them to make better decisions and increase their revenue. The program also assures that the solutions offered are innovative and of high quality. The Virtual Fruits Market app is therefore a useful tool for both producers and consumers.[1]

In people's life, agriculture is essential. It gives humanity enough food supply. In terms of distribution, farmers have historically relied on middlemen to sell their produce, which has limited the market and reduced earnings. While there are many different supply chain difficulties that need to be solved, some businesses concentrate on providing solutions for distribution issues and building channels that allow farm produce to be sold directly to consumers without the need for middlemen. This study presents the creation of an online marketplace that functions as an ecosystem to facilitate meaningful and effective trades between farmers and their respective customers. A platform for business-to-business (B2B) e-commerce in agriculture is created and tested. For front-end development, CSS and HTML are utilized [2]

This project intends to transform the agrochemical distribution model by enabling producers to sell their products directly to customers while keeping costs low. Traditional pesticide distribution involves a number of middlemen, which drives up consumer costs. Our solutions make use of cutting-edge technology and creative approaches to guarantee affordability and accessibility for end users while streamlining supply chains. Agriculture Products aims to create a platform for online buying and selling of agricultural products. Product listings, several produce categories, a secure payment mechanism, user identification, search capabilities, and

adaptable design are just a few of the elements that make the website ideal for users across all platforms. Furthermore, adding features like reviews, ratings, and a user-friendly design boosts website usability and client loyalty. This makes it possible for farmers, suppliers, and customers to seamlessly buy and sell agricultural products [3]

Farmers will be able to sell directly to clients and food processing companies through the use of mobile internet. This article provides farmers with market information using an intuitive mobile application interface. The smartphone application aims to give farmers an efficient and up-to-date means of receiving information. It also supports the native language of farmers, for their convenience. The smartphone software handles farmers as both buyers and vendors. The purpose of this study is to assist farmers in purchasing or selling their agricultural goods and commodities. The buyer may be able to choose from a wide variety of products because the items are designed to be explored.

Numerous filters are available to facilitate browsing. This method claims to offer a simple and enjoyable manner for farmers to sell their commodities and products, since they encounter several challenges in the process. The concept makes business even fair and transparent while enabling farmers to sell their produce at a fair price. On the other side of the same coin are consumers. With the help of this system, customers may choose from a large selection of items, tailor their selection to meet their needs, and even apply price filters.[4]

The goal of this initiative is to use online markets and innovative ways to guarantee fair prices to the agricultural community. a program that provides a means of transporting agricultural goods straight from farmers to customers or shops. With the help of this mobile and online application, farmers, customers, and merchants may acquire and sell the necessary agricultural goods at the optimal, profitable price without the need for an intermediary. The platform's agriculture specialists will evaluate and approve products, assigning grades depending on their quality. This facilitates easy access to all available farm goods. As a result, it offers access and price freedom [5].

Online auction system is a web-based application, in which seller can sell the goods. It is a popular method for buying and selling products. It is developed with the objective of making the auction system reliable, easier, and faster. The objective of the online auction system is that the user can have better choice for their investment. Also, it is time saving and through this system user can invest in their own selected firm. The application allows consumers to bid for the farm produce, thus eradicating middle man and benefiting both farmers and consumers. In this paper we have introduced a dynamic system to sell and buy agricultural products based on auction. The web application will allow the online auction administrator to sell the products through the desired person. Customer must have a valid user id and password to login to the system. In this the admin will post the image and details of the product. The buyer can select the product and bid accordingly. The bidding will have a specific time duration, which will be set by the seller.

At the end of time limit, product will be sold to the highest bidder. Our main aim is to provide a software environment for farmers to gain maximum profit [6]

III. OVERVIEW

- **System Requirements Analysis:** A thorough examination of the specifications was carried out, which included participants from different tiers of the agricultural supply chain. Farmers, wholesalers, quality inspectors, and final customers were all involved in this. Figure 1 demonstrates System design.
- **Flutter Platform Selection:** Google created Flutter as a UI toolkit to create natively built desktop, web, and mobile applications from a single codebase.
- **Widget Development:** The fundamental components of a Flutter user interface are called widgets. Stateless and Stateful widgets are the two primary categories of widgets.

Fig 1: Sytem design[3]

IV. CONCLUSION

The use of Flutter and cloud technology in an agricultural e-commerce platform offers a transformative solution. This system, with its cross-platform capabilities and robust cloud architecture, ensures a user-friendly interface, scalability, and security. Beyond transactions, it provides services such as market information, inventory management, and direct customer connection, fostering efficiency and transparency in the agricultural industry. Despite clear benefits, addressing concerns like data security and regulatory compliance is crucial. The platform serves as a driving force for modernizing agriculture, promoting sustainability and trust between growers and customers. The Virtual Fruits Market software, using the KNN algorithm, exemplifies transparency and enhances the overall dynamics of the Indian agriculture market by closing supply chain gaps.

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